

1 Graphical Abstract

2 **A Refined Gibson-Ashby Model for Functionally Graded Honeycombs with Random Irregu-**
3 **larities**

4 M. J. Beigrezaee, S. K. Jalali, D. Misseroni, N. M. Pugno

1 Highlights

2 **A Refined Gibson-Ashby Model for Functionally Graded Honeycombs with Random Irregu-** 3 **larities**

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- 5 • Functionally graded honeycombs with a random irregularity are parameterized.
- 6 • Exact expression for effective relative elastic modulus is reported
- 7 • The classical Gibson-Ashby model is modified to account for graded variation and irregularity.
- 8 • FE numerical simulations are conducted.
- 9 • Compression tests are performed on 3D-printed samples.